

HOW TO USE THIS MAP:

Uncommon Crowd protocols: The Uncommon Crowd, a DAO, exists on the basis of following protocols, which might help you situate your reflections & encounters:

Here is some information that will help you make choices as you spot points of interest and stage encounters.

Things to KNOW and CONSIDER

1. Participation by Reciprocity: The platform is a space activated and maintained through intra-action and common use of data by its members.

2. Access rights: The platform is a digital public space where agents co-exist. The community sets the guidelines for wanted and unwanted uses of their own data.

3. Data sourcing and Accessibility: The platform is inclusive for different levels of digital fluency, to ensure diversity, representation and plurality of experiences. Personal data curation and interactions with non-human agents fosters ownership.

4. Wellbeing: The platform advocates for community processes to overcome problems. The constant evolution, speculation and adaptation of cooperative practices in the platform is desirable.

What is an anomaly? How do I spot one?

Detecting an anomaly in the public space: Based on the points of interest, you might sense that something (as data) is missing from that space or activity, face some erratic situation from a digital or physical perspective, or find something confusing from the perspective of your role. Record and report this individually to the Ombudsbot chat.

How do I report irresponsible behaviour?

As part of your group chat, you will have access to the reports other agents are collecting on their own explorations. From the perspective of your character, you can consider certain data or information as too personal, invasive, surveillant or excessive, among other factors. You must raise your complaints individually to the Ombudsbot chat, mentioning the agent and the situation you perceive as irresponsible.

Things to KEEP an EYE OUT for

As you move around the city, you will, as asked by your facilitators, stage multiple encounters. We ask that you keep an eye out for these points of interest!

Refer to the map for more.

- Landmark** 🏛️
- Reciprocity (giving & receiving)** 👁️ 👁️
- Crowdedness** 🐜
- A curious place** 🦄
- An anomaly** 😬
- Confusion** 🤔
- Tree/s** 🌳
- Construction site** 🚧

- Play** 🌈
- Green Space** 💚
- Park** 🌳
- Waterway** 🌊
- Congestion** 🐌
- Highstreet** 🏪
- Traces of the past** 🗿
- Mischief** 👁️
- Mingling** 🤝
- Magic** 🌸
- Density** 💎

WELCOME to the UNCOMMON CROWD!

Now that you have become a unique member of this network, its time to take the next step! Today the Uncommon Crowd does not yet have any data. Your objective is to go out into the wild to discover new types of data and feed it back to the platform in order to empower yourself to get what you want out of the data and, by extension, the city.

Be cautious! You never know if and when the platform might override or challenge your actions. Do you have what it takes to be a part of the Uncommon Crowd?

UNCOMMON CROWD

SENSING in the WILD: a more than human workshop

DRS Labs . JUNE 2022 . BILBAO .

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Designed by Mugdha Patil on behalf of DCODE Prototeam Common Sensing.
Táiri, Carlos Guerrero Milan human-machine ombudsman / Grace Turtle crystal ball gazer / Mugdha Patil data medium / Seda Özpatin network therapist / Roy Bender prototeam mentor